

Melhorando a qualidade do adobe em uma aldeia no Mali: uma experiência de cooperação Sul-Sul

Mejorar la calidad de adobe en una aldea de Mali: una experiencia de cooperación Sur-Sur

Improving adobes quality on village in Mali: an experience of South–South cooperation

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ABSTRACT

Adobe is widely used in the village of Bandiagará II and surrounding areas in Mali, Africa. The high applicability of this vernacular technique in local constructions is due to numerous factors. The main ones are: low cost, thermal comfort, minimal water and energy consumption, and the available soil that avoids transportation costs. This simple technique has excellent potential for training, to provide dignified and comfortable housing. However, pathologies were observed in local constructions from production to execution. Therefore, the objective of this work was to study the local soil and present techniques and possibilities for stabilization to ensure better physical and mechanical quality of the adobes. Expedient tests and laboratory assays evaluated the soil regarding grain size and mineralogical origin. The adobes were produced according to the recommendation of ABNT NBR 16.814:2020 - Adobe: requirements and testing methods. The treatments used "in natura" soil (CT-control); soil corrected with sand; stabilization with "synthetic termite saliva" at 1:1,000, 1:1,500, and 1:2,000 with reagents aluminum sulfate $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ at 1:5,000 (AST) and hydrated lime $Ca(OH)_2$ (HLT) at 1.5% and 2% separately. The dimensions adopted for themolds were $30 \times 15 \times 8 \text{ cm}^3$ and $38 \times 18 \times 8 \text{ cm}^3$. The treatments with "synthetic termite saliva" at 1:1,500 with reagents aluminum sulfate $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ at 1:5,000 and hydrated lime $Ca(OH)_2$ at 1.5% and 2% separately showed significant improvement in water absorption reduction and greater soil cohesion. Regarding the compressive strength for the "in natura" soil (CT), it was 0.6 MPa, with superior results for stabilization with "synthetic termite saliva" at 1:1,500 of 1.8M Pa for AST at 1:5,000 and 2.27 MPa for HLT at 2%. Excellent results were obtained in waterproofing

Keywords: Sustainability, "Synthetic termite saliva", Waterproofing, Compressive strength, Water absorption.

RESÚMEN

El adobe es ampliamente utilizado en la aldea de Bandiagará II y sus alrededores en Mali, África. La alta aplicabilidad de esta técnica vernácula en las construcciones locales se debe a numerosos factores. Los principales son: bajo costo, confort térmico, consumo mínimo de agua y energía, y la disponibilidad de suelo que evita costos de transporte. Esta sencilla técnica tiene un excelente potencial para la capacitación y la provisión de viviendas dignas y confortables. Sin embargo, se observaron patologías en las construcciones locales desde la producción hasta la ejecución. Por lo tanto, el objetivo de este trabajo fue estudiar el suelo local y presentar técnicas y posibilidades de estabilización para asegurar

una mejor calidad física y mecánica de los adobes. Se realizaron pruebas de conveniencia y ensayos de laboratorio para evaluar el suelo en cuanto a tamaño de grano y origen mineralógico. Los adobes se produjeron de acuerdo con la recomendación de la norma ABNT NBR 16.814:2020 - Adobe: requisitos y métodos de prueba. Los tratamientos utilizados fueron suelo "in natura" (control CT); suelo corregido con arena; Estabilización con saliva sintética de termitas a 1:1000, 1:1500 y 1:2000 con los reactivos sulfato de aluminio $Al_2(SO_3)_3$ a 1:5000 (TSA) y cal hidratada $Ca(OH)_2$ (TCH) al 1,5 % y al 2 %, respectivamente. Las dimensiones de los moldes fueron 30 x 15 x 8 cm³ y 38 x 18 x 8 cm³. Los tratamientos con saliva sintética de termitas a 1:1500 con los reactivos sulfato de aluminio $Al_2(SO_3)_3$ a 1:5000 y cal hidratada $Ca(OH)_2$ al 1,5 % y al 2 %, respectivamente, mostraron una mejora significativa en la reducción de la absorción de agua y una mayor cohesión del suelo. Respecto a la resistencia a la compresión para el suelo "in natura" (TC) fue de 0,6 MPa, con resultados superiores para la estabilización con "saliva sintética de termitas" a 1:1.500 de 1,8 MPa para AST a 1:5.000 y 2,27 MPa para HLT al 2%. Se obtuvieron excelentes resultados en la impermeabilización de muros de adobe con una solución al 5% de "baba sintética de termitas" y agua 1L:20L ("baba sintética de termitas":agua) y una solución al 1% de reactivo $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ y agua 200g:20L ($Al_2(SO_4)_3$:agua).

Palabras clave: Sostenibilidad, "Saliva sintética de termitas", Impermeabilización, Resistencia a la compresión, Absorción de agua.

RESUMO

O adobe é amplamente utilizado na vila de Bandiagará II e áreas adjacentes, no Mali, África. A alta aplicabilidade dessa técnica vernacular em construções locais se deve a inúmeros fatores. Os principais são: baixo custo, conforto térmico, consumo mínimo de água e energia e solo disponível, o que evita custos de transporte. Essa técnica simples tem excelente potencial para treinamento, para proporcionar moradias dignas e confortáveis. No entanto, patologias foram observadas em construções locais, desde a produção até a execução. Portanto, o objetivo deste trabalho foi estudar o solo local e apresentar técnicas e possibilidades de estabilização para garantir melhor qualidade física e mecânica dos adobes. Ensaio de expediente e ensaio de laboratório avaliaram o solo quanto à granulometria e origem mineralógica. Os adobes foram produzidos de acordo com a recomendação da ABNT NBR 16.814:2020 - Adobe: requisitos e métodos de ensaio. Os tratamentos utilizados foram solo "in natura" (CT-controle); solo corrigido com areia; estabilização com "saliva sintética de cupim" nas proporções 1:1.000, 1:1.500 e 1:2.000 com os reagentes sulfato de alumínio $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ na proporção 1:5.000 (TSA) e cal hidratada $Ca(OH)_2$ (TCH) nas proporções 1,5% e 2%, separadamente. As dimensões adotadas para os moldes foram 30x15x8 cm³ e 38x18x8 cm³. Os tratamentos com "baba de cupim sintética" na proporção 1:1.500 com os reagentes sulfato de alumínio $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ na proporção 1:5.000 e cal hidratada $Ca(OH)_2$ nas proporções 1,5% e 2%, separadamente, apresentaram melhora significativa na redução da absorção de água e maior coesão do solo. Em relação à resistência à compressão do solo "in natura" (TC), esta foi de 0,6 MPa, com resultados superiores para a estabilização com "baba de cupim sintética" a 1:1.500 de 1,8 MPa para TSA a 1:5.000 e 2,27 MPa para TCH a 2%. Excelentes resultados foram obtidos em impermeabilização de paredes de adobe com solução a 5% de "baba de cupim sintética" e água 1L:20L ("baba de cupim sintética": água) e solução a 1% de reagente $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ e água 200g: 20L ($Al_2(SO_4)_3$: água).

Palavras-chave: Sustentabilidade, "Baba de cupim sintética", Impermeabilização, Resistência à compressão, Absorção de água.

DESCRIPTION OF THE EXPERIENCE

Originally from the Bandiagara Cliffs near Mopti, at the centre of the Mali, the Dogon people migrated to Bandiagara II due to conflicts in the north. The village is now geographically situated in the Koutiala region and has an estimated population of 630 inhabitants. It lies in a semi-arid climate.

Annual rainfall ranges between 600 and 900 mm, supporting primarily rainfed cotton as the main crop, followed by cereals and livestock (World Bank, 2023). Cooperation between Brazil and Mali is facilitated through the CMDT and the Brazilian Cooperation Agency (ABC), with a focus on increasing cotton production (Agência Brasileira de Cooperação ABC, 2024).

With the aim of improving the physical and mechanical properties of adobes and existing buildings, in three different missions lasting one week each, we evaluated the buildings considering: foundation, executive methods, masonry, coating and existing pathologies (Figure 1).

Figura 1. Local diagnosis

Source: Authors, 2024

Through discussions with the local community, we understood the advantages and challenges of adobe. Following the diagnostic results, the local soil was studied for granulometry and mineralogy through rapid and laboratory tests. The adobes were produced according to the recommendation of ABNT NBR 16.814:2020 - Adobe: requirements and test methods. The treatments used were "in natura" soil (CT-control); soil amended with sand; stabilization with "synthetic termite slime" in proportions of 1:1,000, 1:1,500, and 1:2,000 with the reagents aluminum sulfate $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ in a proportion of 1:5,000 (AST) and hydrated lime $Ca(OH)_2$ (HLT) in proportions of 1.5% and 2%, separately. The dimensions adopted for the molds were $30 \times 15 \times 8 \text{ cm}^3$ and $38 \times 18 \times 8 \text{ cm}^3$. The adobes were produced in artisanal way (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Production of adobes in proposed methodology and treatments.

Source: Authors, 2024

Samples were taken for physical-mechanical testing. The treatments with "synthetic termite saliva" at 1:1,500 with reagents aluminum sulfate $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ at 1:5,000 and hydrated lime $Ca(OH)_2$ at 1.5% and 2% separately showed significant improvement in water absorption reduction and greater soil cohesion. The quick volumetric contraction test demonstrated that there was no significant variation between treatments. The samples did not show cracks and the contraction was within the permitted limit. Regarding the compressive strength for the "in natura" soil (CT), it was 0.6 MPa, with superior results for stabilization with "synthetic termite saliva" at 1:1,500 of 1.8M Pa for AST at 1:5,000 and 2.27 MPa for HLT at 2% (Figure 3).

Figure 3.. The results of the volumetric contraction test; test specimens for compressive strength testing; and the test on the Universal Machine.

Source: Authors, 2024

Figure 4 Shows the waterproofing of the adobe walls, the following was applied: "synthetic termite saliva" with a 5% solution in water 1L:20L ("synthetic termite saliva":water) and a 1% solution of $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ reagent and water 200g:20L ($Al_2(SO_4)_3$:water).

Figura 4. Guidance on the application of waterproofing solutions, and comparison of walls with and without the formulation.

Source: Authors, 2024.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The treatments with "synthetic termite saliva" at 1:1,500 with reagents aluminum sulfate $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ at 1:5,000 and hydrated lime $Ca(OH)_2$ at 1.5% and 2% separately showed significant improvement in water absorption reduction and greater soil cohesion. Regarding the compressive strength for the "in natura" soil (CT), it was 0.6 MPa, with superior results for stabilization with "synthetic termite saliva" at 1:1,500 of 1.8MPa for AST at 1:5,000 and 2.27 MPa for HLT at 2%. Excellent results were obtained in waterproofing.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This experience highlights the role of South–South cooperation in addressing complex challenges in vulnerable regions and provides a replicable model for other rural communities in Sub-Saharan Africa. In future work, booklets will be produced to provide guidance on good construction practices, disease prevention, and successful stabilization of adobes in the village.

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